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Socioeconomic characteristics and production problems of terrace rice farmers in Senapati district of Manipur

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Abstract

The present study entitled “Socioeconomic characteristics and production problems of terrace rice farmers in Senapati district of Manipur” was conducted in the year 2021-2022 with a sample size of 90 respondents chosen through probability proportional to size sampling technique. The study covered four villages of Sadar Hills West and Mao-maram blocks and primary data on all the relevant aspects was collected through personal interview method. The findings of the study revealed that the average operational land holding was found to be 0.71 hectares which was 0.52 and 1.17 hectares on marginal and small farms respectively. The average family size of marginal, small and overall farmers was 4.67, 8.73 and 5.84 respectively and the literacy rate of marginal farmers was 89.06 percent and that of small farmers was 84.62 percent. The major problems in cultivation of terrace rice production were lack of irrigation facilities, credit facilities followed by small size of land holdings and high labour cost.

Keywords: Terrace, rice, socioeconomic, Manipur, production problems

1. Introduction

Globally, rice is the staple food of 3.5 billion people, which is about half the world's population and is grown in >100 countries with 90% of the total global production from Asia. Rice has shaped the cultures, diets and economies of thousands of millions of people and is life for more than half of the humanity. Wheat, rice, and maize account for over 50% of all the calories consumed by people worldwide (Gnanamanickam, 2009) ^[2]. Rice accounts for 43 percent of the country's total food grain production and 46 percent of total cereal production (Narala and Zala, 2010) ^[4]. The production of rice has increased at compounded annual growth rate (CGAR) of 2.7 percent during last six years i.e., 2015-16 to 2020-21 (GoI, 2022) ^[3]. About 90 percent of gross cropped area (GCA) is under paddy cultivation in Manipur (Singha and Mishra, 2015) ^[6]. During the post green revolution period introduction of improved varieties, pushed the rice yield by about 40 percent in the North eastern hilly region (Panda and Reddy, 1989) ^[5]. In terms of area, production and consumption, rice is the only important food crop in the state of Manipur (Devi and Singh, 2014) ^[1]. Rice is the staple food of Manipur and is grown in both the hill and valley districts. Terrace farming is the only practical solution for hilly agricultural land and is mainly practised in hilly areas and is a method of growing crops on sides of hills or mountains by planting on graduated terraces that have been carved out of slope. Although labour-intensive, this technique has been successfully used to increase the amount of arable land in terrains with varying topographies and to lower soil erosion and water loss. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to analyse the Socioeconomic characteristics and production problems of terrace rice farmers in Senapati district of Manipur.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the study area

The present study was conducted in Manipur which covers a geographical area of 22,327 square kilometres (8,621 sq. mi.) lying 790 m above msl. The state lies between 23.80° N to 25.68° N latitude and 93.03° E to 94.78° E longitude and is bounded by the Indian states of Nagaland to the north, Mizoram to the south west, Assam to the west and by Myanmar (Burma) to the south and east. Among the five hill districts of Manipur, Senapati district was selected purposively for the research study. The district is under humid sub-tropical climate with temperature ranging from a minimum of 3.4 °C to a maximum of 34.1 °C. The annual rainfall ranges from 670 mm to 1,450 mm.

2.2 Sampling plan

Senapati district has the highest area and production under terrace rice. Thus, Senapati district was purposively selected for the study. Out of six blocks in the Senapati district, blocks having the highest acreage under terrace rice Sadar Hills West and Mao-maram blocks were selected purposively. A list of 4 villages two from each block were selected. At final stage, the growers in the village were enlisted and preliminary information on landholdings, the area under terrace rice was collected with the help of respective village headmen and 90 terrace rice growers were selected by using Probability Proportional to Size sampling technique. The primary data was collected from the sample farmers through personal interview method with the help of a pre-tested and well-structured schedule.

2.3 Analytical tools

The data pertaining to the respondents' socioeconomic profile was presented using descriptive or tabular analysis, which involved the computation of means and percentages. Various problems associated with the production of terrace rice; multiple responses of producers were taken into consideration for analysis. Information regarding the problems faced by the farmers in the production of terrace rice were collected by enquiring the farmers. With the help of descriptive statistical tools such as frequency distribution and percentage, the problems are ranked.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Farm size

The size of the farm is an important factor that determines the socioeconomic well-being of the family in particular and the area under the consideration at large. The average size of land holding with farm workers on different categories of terrace rice growing sample farmers is presented below (Table 1). The average size of operational holding was found to be 0.52 and 1.17 hectares at marginal and small farms respectively. Majority of the sampled respondents were found to be in marginal category. It can be seen that majority (71.11 percent) of the sample respondents had an operational land holding of less than 1 ha, 28.89 percent had 1-2 ha.

Table 1: Size of sample terrace rice growing farms and farm workers

Sl. No.	Particular	Farm Category		
		Marginal	Small	Overall
1.	No of farms	64 (71.11)	26 (28.89)	90 (100)
2.	Average size of farm (ha)	0.52	1.17	0.71
3.	Farm workers			
	Male	88 (51.16)	74 (58.73)	162 (54.36)
	Female (male equivalent)	84 (48.84)	52 (41.27)	136 (45.64)
4.	Total workers	172 (100)	126 (100)	298 (100)

Note: Figures in parentheses denotes the percentage to the respective total

3.2 Size of family

Table 2 shows the total family size of terrace rice growing sample farms. The average number of adults worked out to be 73.91 percent (39.46% male and 34.45% female) and 79.73 percent (44.93% male and 34.8% female) in marginal and small farms respectively. The results show that the average family size of marginal, small and overall farmers was 4.67, 8.73 and 5.84 respectively.

Table 2: Family size and composition of sample farm family, (Persons)

Sl. No.	Particular	Farm Category		
		Marginal	Small	Overall
1.	No. of households	64	26	90
2.	Average size of family	4.67	8.73	5.84
3.	Children			
	Male	43 (14.38)	27 (11.89)	70 (13.31)
	Female	35 (11.71)	19 (8.37)	54 (10.27)
4.	Adult			
	Male	118 (39.46)	102 (44.93)	220 (41.83)
	Female	103 (34.45)	79 (34.8)	182 (34.6)
5.	Total family size	299 (100)	227 (100)	526 (100)

Note: Figures in parentheses denotes the percentage to the respective total

3.3 Distribution of sample households according to the age of farmers

Socio-economic transformation and adoption of innovations are greatly influenced by the age of the decision maker. The age of an individual has a great influence on his/her ability to take part in economic activities and get more benefit from the ongoing enterprise.

Table 3 reveals that in marginal and small farms 34.38 and 38.46 percent of the farmers were in the age group of 36-45 and 46-55 years respectively. Being younger in age, it is therefore presumed that the marginal farmers would be more likely to be receptive for a change than the small farmers. Overall, the maximum number of farmers are in the age group of 36-45(32.22%) and 46-55 years (28.89%), followed by those in the age group of 25-35 years (23.33%) and so on. Most of the sample farmers are in younger to middle age group; hence any innovative change will be highly responsive if farmers are more in younger age group.

Table 3: Distribution of sample households according to the age of the farmers for different categories of sample farms, (Persons)

Sl. No.	Age group	Farm Category		
		Marginal	Small	Overall
1	25-35	21 (32.81)	0 (0)	21 (23.33)
2	36-45	22 (34.38)	7 (26.92)	29 (32.22)
3	46-55	16 (25)	10 (38.46)	26 (28.89)
4	56-65	4 (6.25)	5 (19.23)	9 (10)
5	Above 65	1 (1.56)	4 (15.38)	5 (5.56)
6	Total	64 (100)	26 (100)	90 (100)

Note: Figures in parentheses denotes the percentage to the respective total

3.4 Educational status

Education equips the individual with the skills to read, write, record, receive training and seek information from the available sources. The distribution of farmers according to education level is given in Table 4. It is evident from the table that in overall, 12.22 percent of the farmers were illiterate, with a higher illiteracy in case of small farmers (15.38%) against 10.94 percent in marginal farms. Among the literates, in overall farm, 35.56 percent of the farmers are educated up to middle school, which is followed by primary school (30%). In both the categories of farms, the farmers who are educated up to middle school are highest in number (35.94% and 34.62%) in marginal and small farms respectively. The literacy rate of marginal farmers was 89.06 percent and that of small farmers was 84.62 percent.

Table 4: Educational status of the sample farmers, (Persons)

Sl. No.	Level of education	Farm Category		
		Marginal	Small	Overall
1.	Illiterate	7 (10.94)	4 (15.38)	11 (12.22)
2.	Primary school	21 (32.81)	6 (23.08)	27 (30)
3.	Middle school	23 (35.94)	9 (34.62)	32 (35.56)
4.	Secondary	8 (12.5)	3 (11.54)	11 (12.22)
5.	Higher Secondary	3 (4.69)	2 (7.69)	5 (5.56)
6.	Graduate and above	2 (3.13)	2 (7.69)	4 (4.44)
7.	Total	64 (100)	26 (100)	90 (100)
8.	Literacy rate (%)	89.06	84.62	87.78

Note: Figures in parentheses denotes the percentage to the respective total

3.5 Size of land holding

Land is the basic resource in an agrarian economy. Land holdings attain a special status in determining the income generation pattern of land holdings thus attains significance not only from the point of view of rural economy but also from the overall welfare point of view.

Table 5 presents the farm category wise distribution of land

holding of terrace rice growing sample farmers. It is evident from the table that 100 percent of the total operational holding were owned land in both marginal and small farms.

Table 5: Land use pattern of sample farms, (Area in ha)

Particular	Farm Category		
	Marginal	Small	Overall
Owned land	0.52 (100)	1.17 (100)	0.71 (100)
Leased-in land	0	0	0
Total operational holding	0.52 (100)	1.17 (100)	0.71 (100)

Note: Figures in parentheses denotes the percentage to the respective total

3.6 Production problems faced by the terrace rice farmers

The terrace rice farmers had to overcome a variety of problems which was found out through personal interview. The major problems were identified and ranked based on the severity as perceived by the sample farmers. Table 6 represents the major production problems faced by the sample farmers.

Table 6: Production problems faced by sample farmers during production of terrace rice

Sl. No.	Problems	Marginal	Small	Overall	Percentage
1.	Lack of irrigation facilities	59	24	83	92
2.	Lack of credit facility	56	23	79	88
3.	Small size of land holdings	52	21	73	81
4.	High labour cost	49	19	68	76
5.	Low price for output	46	16	62	69
6.	Problem of high weed occurrence	43	17	60	67
7.	Heavy infestation of pests and diseases	41	15	56	62
8.	Crop failure	40	13	53	59
9.	Labour scarcity	37	13	50	56
10.	Lack of technical guidance	34	14	48	53
11.	Non availability of fertilizers on time	32	13	45	50
12.	Non availability of seed on time	29	12	41	46
13.	Mud slide	25	11	36	40

About 92 percent of the farmers in the study area claimed that lack of irrigation facilities to be the most severe problem and was assigned as first rank because irrigation was one of the most important inputs which reflects on the yield of the crop. The farmers claimed that irrigation system adopted in the study area was mainly rainfed and thus the water scarcity was the common problem faced by the farmers. Despite the availability of a number of financial institutions, credit facilities were reported to be very limited, claimed by 88% of the total sample farms, and was ranked second. They could not get the credit from the institutional agencies in time, which made them borrow from money lenders who charged a high rate of interest.

Around 81 percent of the farmers reported the problem of small size of land holdings because individual farmers in hills have widely dispersed terraced fields at different altitudes. About 76 and 69 percent of the sample farmers complained that the high cost of labour and low price of output as one of the major problems and were assigned fourth and fifth rank respectively. farmers. The weed occurrence was the most constraint reported by around 67 percent of the sample farmers. Nearly 62 percent of the farmers reported a heavy infestation of pests and diseases in their crop and they were also unaware of the proper usage of plant protection chemicals. About 59 percent of the farmers reported the problem of crop failure and was assigned eighth rank. Labour

scarcity was another problem.

It is evident from the table that 56 percent of the farmers faced the problem of non-availability of labour on time. 53 percent of the respondents in the study area were facing the problem of technical guidance. It was mainly because dissemination of the information by the extension agents was weak. About 50 and 46 percent of the farmers claimed the non-availability of fertilizers and seed on time as eleventh and twelfth rank. During periods of heavy rainfall, nearly 40% of all terrace rice farmers experienced the problem of mud slides.

4. Conclusion

The average farm size was found to be 0.52 ha, 1.17 ha and 0.71 ha in marginal, small and overall farms respectively. It was found that maximum proportion of about 34.38 percent of the farmers were in the age group of 36-45 years in marginal farms and 38.46 percent of the farmers in small farms were in the age group of 46-55 years. About 87.78 percent sample farmers were found to be literate in overall farms and most of them were educated up to middle school level (35.56). The literacy rate was found to be higher for marginal category farmers (89.06) than small category farmers (84.62). There were no proportions of leased-in land in marginal, small and overall farms. About 92 percent of the farmers in the study area claimed that lack of irrigation facilities to be the most

severe problem. Besides these, lack of credit facilities and small size of land holdings were reported as the severe production constraints by 88 and 81 percent of the farmers, respectively.

5. Policy implication

Increase in credit availabilities would help in enhancing the production of terrace rice. Effort should be made to strengthen the linkage between the financial institutions and the farmers so that the farmer can come forward easily for financial assistance. Efforts should be made for vital inputs particularly seeds, fertilizers and pesticides at reasonable prices and in adequate quantities to the farmers at required time. As farmers are facing the problem of high labour cost, it can only be decreased by mechanizing the agriculture.

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